

IDENTIFICATION OF DAMAGE VARIABLE IN CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE WITH DIFFERENT BEHAVIOUR IN TENSION AND COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

A continuum damage mechanics model for elastic deformation of ceramic matrix composites is presented. This model describes simultaneously the difference between the damaging processes under compressive and tensile loading types and damage induced anisotropy (or initial anisotropy). The proposed constitutive equations contain joint invariants of the stress tensor and some material tensors. A scalar damage variable for an initially anisotropic material and a second-order damage tensor in the case of damage induced anisotropy are considered. Specific constitutive equations with a smaller number of material parameters and invariants are obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Direct measurement of physical quantities, like damage parameters of ceramic matrix composites, is connected with great experimental difficulties. Therefore different methods of nondirect measurements of damage parameters play an important role in modern engineering mechanics. One of these methods bases on the influence of elastic damage and uses the information about the decrease of the elasticity modulus of the damaged material.

Many brittle matrix composites show [1,2] in basic experiments anisotropic behaviour (initial anisotropy or damage induced anisotropy) and the difference between the damaging processes under tensile and compressive loading types. But even in the elastic case, up to now, there is no theory which is able to reproduce simultaneously both the initial anisotropy and the different damage in tension and compression. The absence of this theory makes it impossible to perform the identification of damage variables for such material behaviour.

The aim of this paper is to solve this important problem. In the following small elastic strains in isothermal processes are considered.

FORMULATION OF CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

To describe the elastic anisotropic damage we can start from the consideration of deformation in an isotropic medium. For this purpose the mentioned "isotropic concept" [3] will be used by substituting a mapped stress tensor. First let us consider the isotropic case without damage.

The stress-strain relations for elastic behaviour are based on the assumption of the existence of a potential F . For isotropic materials this potential $F = F(\underline{\sigma})$ is a scalar-valued tensor function of the CAUCHY stress tensor $\underline{\sigma}$. It is evident from the theory of isotropic tensor functions that in an isotropic medium an elastic potential

$$F = F[J_1(\underline{\sigma}), J_2(\underline{\sigma}), J_3(\underline{\sigma})] \quad (1)$$

can depend only on the invariants

$$J_1(\underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{\delta}, \quad J_2(\underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{\sigma}, \quad J_3(\underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\sigma} \cdot (\underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{\sigma}) \quad (2)$$

of the stress tensor. Here, the symbol (\cdot) denotes the scalar product, $\underline{\delta}$ represents Kronecker's tensor.

Taking into consideration the above mentioned assumption, the potential F in (1) can be written in the form

$$F = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_e^2 \quad (3)$$

where the equivalent stress σ_e has the following structure [4]

$$\sigma_e = \sigma_2 + \alpha \sigma_1 + \gamma \sigma_3 \quad (4)$$

Here

$$\sigma_1 = B J_1(\underline{\sigma}), \quad \sigma_2^2 = A J_1^2(\underline{\sigma}) + C J_2(\underline{\sigma}), \quad \sigma_3^3 = D J_1^3(\underline{\sigma}) + K J_1(\underline{\sigma}) J_2(\underline{\sigma}) + L J_3(\underline{\sigma}) \quad (5)$$

are scalar functions of the stress invariants; A, B, C, D, K, L are some material parameters; α, γ are numerical coefficients taking into account the influence of linear and cubic invariants in the expression (4) for σ_e .

By analogy with the concept of Krajcinovic and Fonseka [5], let us describe the stress-strain state of the damaged isotropic material on the base of the relations (1)-(5) for the undamaged material with the parameters A, B, C, D, K, L in its replaced by the damage scalar functions $\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}, \tilde{C}, \tilde{D}, \tilde{K}, \tilde{L}$, respectively.

We then use the assumption [3] that the anisotropy of the material is entirely involved in a fourth rank tensor $\underline{\underline{M}}$, and the anisotropic behaviour is described by the linear transformation

$$\underline{\tau} = \underline{\underline{M}} \cdot \underline{\sigma} \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{\sigma}$ is the CAUCHY stress tensor for an anisotropic medium. By analogy with relation (5) the basic invariants of the image tensor (6) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1(\underline{\tau}) &\equiv \sigma_1(\underline{\underline{b}}, \underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\underline{b}} \cdot \underline{\sigma}, & \sigma_2^2(\underline{\tau}) &\equiv \sigma_2^2(\underline{\underline{a}}, \underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{\underline{a}} \cdot \underline{\sigma} \\ \sigma_3^3(\underline{\tau}) &\equiv \sigma_3^3(\underline{\underline{c}}, \underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\sigma} \cdot (\underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{\underline{c}} \cdot \underline{\sigma}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

if we define the material tensors $\underline{\underline{b}}, \underline{\underline{a}}, \underline{\underline{c}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{b}_{ij} &\equiv \tilde{B} M_{ijpp}, \quad \tilde{a}_{ijkl} = \tilde{A} M_{ijpp} M_{klqq} + \tilde{C} M_{ijpq} M_{klpq} \\ \tilde{c}_{ijklmn} &= \tilde{D} M_{ijpp} M_{klqq} M_{mnnr} + \tilde{K} M_{ijpp} M_{klqr} M_{mnqr} + \tilde{L} M_{ijrs} M_{klsp} M_{mnpr} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Here we utilize Einstein's summation convention. The invariants in Eqn (7) are elements of the system of joint invariants, which are only considered, and the material tensors are influenced by damage.

As known, the elastic infinitesimal strain tensor $\underline{\varepsilon}$ is determined by the rule

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} \quad (9)$$

Therefore, using Eqns (3), (4) and the relations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} &= \sigma_e \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_2}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} + \alpha \frac{\partial \sigma_1}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} + \gamma \frac{\partial \sigma_3}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} \right), \quad \frac{\partial \sigma_2}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} = \frac{\underline{\underline{\underline{a}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_2} \\ \frac{\partial \sigma_1}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} &= \underline{\underline{\underline{b}}}, \quad \frac{\partial \sigma_3}{\partial \underline{\sigma}} = \frac{\underline{\sigma} \cdot \cdot \underline{\underline{\underline{c}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_3^2} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

we arrive at the constitutive equation

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \sigma_e \left(\frac{\underline{\underline{\underline{a}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_2} + \alpha \underline{\underline{\underline{b}}} + \gamma \frac{\underline{\sigma} \cdot \cdot \underline{\underline{\underline{c}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_3^2} \right) \quad (11)$$

for the damaged anisotropic materials. This equation can be represented in canonical form

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \underline{\underline{\underline{H}}} + \underline{\underline{\underline{P}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma} + \left(\underline{\underline{\underline{Q}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma} \right) \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma} \quad (12)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\underline{H}}}$, $\underline{\underline{\underline{P}}}$, $\underline{\underline{\underline{Q}}}$ are tensor functions depending on the stress tensor and the material tensors.

The constitutive equation (11) has a nonlinear-tensor structure and has a general form. That is why we analyse possible specific relations, resulting from (11) and containing a smaller number of parameters.

For example, if we assume $\gamma = 0$, we arrive at the linear-tensor equation

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \sigma_e \left(\frac{\underline{\underline{\underline{a}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_2} + \alpha \underline{\underline{\underline{b}}} \right) \quad (13)$$

where

$$\sigma_e = \sigma_e(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\underline{\underline{b}}}, \underline{\underline{\underline{a}}}) \quad (14)$$

In the case of $\alpha = 0$ Eqn (11) is transformed into the nonlinear-tensor equation

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \sigma_e \left(\frac{\underline{\underline{\underline{a}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_2} + \gamma \frac{\underline{\sigma} \cdot \cdot \underline{\underline{\underline{c}}} \cdot \cdot \underline{\sigma}}{\sigma_3^2} \right) \quad (15)$$

with the equivalent stress

$$\sigma_e = \sigma_e(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\tilde{a}}, \underline{\tilde{c}}) \quad (16)$$

Using the conditions $\alpha = \gamma = 0$, from the relation (11) we obtain Hooke's law

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \underline{\tilde{a}} \cdot \underline{\sigma} \quad (17)$$

Then let us consider the description of the anisotropic damage in the following two different situations.

- An anisotropic damage in the first case is connected with the initial symmetries of such an initially anisotropic material as ceramic matrix composites. In this situation the orientation of microcracks corresponds to the principal axes of the anisotropy of the material. The damage variable can be considered as a scalar.
- A more complex case is connected with the damage induced anisotropy under complex loading conditions. In this situation the damage has its own directionalities, and the damage variable is a vector function or tensor function.

DAMAGE IN INITIALLY ANISOTROPIC MATERIALS

For initially anisotropic material, in which microcracks are oriented parallel to the principal axes of the anisotropy, let us introduce the damage variable as a scalar ω . This variable shall be defined in the form

$$\omega = 1 - \chi^{-2}, \quad \chi = \frac{\sigma_e}{\Sigma_e} \quad (18)$$

where Σ_e is the initial value of the equivalent stress (4).

For initially orthotropic material the constitutive equation (13) is written in such a form in a coordinate system whose axes coincide with the principal directions of anisotropy:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{11} = \sigma_e \left(\frac{\tilde{a}_{1111}\sigma_{11} + \tilde{a}_{1122}\sigma_{22} + \tilde{a}_{1133}\sigma_{33}}{\sigma_2} + \alpha \tilde{b}_{11} + \gamma \frac{\tilde{c}_{111111}\sigma_{11}^2 + \tilde{c}_{112222}\sigma_{22}^2 + \tilde{c}_{113333}\sigma_{33}^2}{\sigma_3^2} + \right. \\ \left. + 2\gamma \frac{\tilde{c}_{111122}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + \tilde{c}_{111133}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33} + \tilde{c}_{112233}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{\sigma_3^2} + \right. \\ \left. + 4\gamma \frac{\tilde{c}_{111212}\sigma_{12}^2 + \tilde{c}_{112323}\sigma_{23}^2 + \tilde{c}_{111313}\sigma_{13}^2}{\sigma_3^2} \right) \quad (1, 2, 3) \\ \varepsilon_{12} = 2\sigma_e \left(\frac{\tilde{a}_{1212}\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_2} + 2\gamma \frac{\tilde{c}_{121211}\sigma_{12}\sigma_{11} + \tilde{c}_{121222}\sigma_{12}\sigma_{22} + \tilde{c}_{121233}\sigma_{12}\sigma_{33}}{\sigma_3^2} + \right. \\ \left. + 4\gamma \frac{\tilde{c}_{122313}\sigma_{23}\sigma_{13}}{\sigma_3^2} \right) \quad (1, 2, 3) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Here

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_1 &= \tilde{b}_{11}\sigma_{11} + \tilde{b}_{22}\sigma_{22} + \tilde{b}_{33}\sigma_{33} \\
 \sigma_2^2 &= \tilde{a}_{1111}\sigma_{11}^2 + \tilde{a}_{2222}\sigma_{22}^2 + \tilde{a}_{3333}\sigma_{33}^2 + 2\tilde{a}_{1122}\sigma_{12}^2 + 2\tilde{a}_{2323}\sigma_{23}^2 + 4\tilde{a}_{1212}\sigma_{12}^2 + \\
 &\quad + 4\tilde{a}_{2323}\sigma_{23}^2 + 4\tilde{a}_{1313}\sigma_{13}^2 \\
 \sigma_3^3 &= \tilde{c}_{111111}\sigma_{11}^3 + \tilde{c}_{222222}\sigma_{22}^3 + \tilde{c}_{333333}\sigma_{33}^3 + 3\tilde{c}_{111122}\sigma_{11}^2\sigma_{22} + 3\tilde{c}_{111133}\sigma_{11}^2\sigma_{33} + \\
 &\quad + 3\tilde{c}_{222211}\sigma_{22}^2\sigma_{11} + 3\tilde{c}_{222233}\sigma_{22}^2\sigma_{33} + 3\tilde{c}_{333311}\sigma_{33}^2\sigma_{11} + 3\tilde{c}_{333322}\sigma_{33}^2\sigma_{22} + \\
 &\quad + 6\tilde{c}_{112233}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} + 12\tilde{c}_{121211}\sigma_{12}^2\sigma_{11} + 12\tilde{c}_{121222}\sigma_{12}^2\sigma_{22} + 12\tilde{c}_{121233}\sigma_{12}^2\sigma_{33} + \\
 &\quad + 12\tilde{c}_{232311}\sigma_{23}^2\sigma_{11} + 12\tilde{c}_{232322}\sigma_{23}^2\sigma_{22} + 12\tilde{c}_{232333}\sigma_{23}^2\sigma_{33} + 12\tilde{c}_{131311}\sigma_{13}^2\sigma_{11} + \\
 &\quad + 12\tilde{c}_{131322}\sigma_{13}^2\sigma_{22} + 12\tilde{c}_{131333}\sigma_{13}^2\sigma_{33} + 48\tilde{c}_{122313}\sigma_{12}\sigma_{23}\sigma_{13}
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

the number of the different parameters $\tilde{b}_{ij} - 3, \tilde{a}_{ijkl} - 9, \tilde{c}_{ijklmn} - 20$.

Let us return to the definition of the damage variable according to Eqn (18). Using Eqns (19), (20), it is not difficult to obtain such relation describing the damage in the basic experiments:

- tension in the principal direction 1

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_1^+}{E_1^+} \tag{21}$$

- compression in the principal direction 1

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_1^-}{E_1^-} \tag{22}$$

- tension in the principal direction 2

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_2^+}{E_2^+} \tag{23}$$

- compression in the direction 2

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_2^-}{E_2^-} \tag{24}$$

- pure torsion

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{\tilde{G}_{12}}{G_{12}} \tag{25}$$

Here $E_1^+, E_1^-, E_2^+, E_2^-, G_{12}$ and $\tilde{E}_1^+, \tilde{E}_1^-, \tilde{E}_2^+, \tilde{E}_2^-, \tilde{G}_{12}$ are the initial values and the sesant values of the elastic constants of the orthotropic damaged material.

Remark 1. When $\tilde{E}_1^+ = E_1^+, \tilde{E}_1^- = E_1^-, \tilde{E}_2^+ = E_2^+, \tilde{E}_2^- = E_2^-, \tilde{G}_{12} = G_{12}$, we have from Eqns (21) - (25) that $\omega \equiv \omega_0 = 0$. In fact, the initial value of the damage variable is $\omega_0 > 0$. But, since $\omega_0 \ll 1$, we can assume that $\omega_0 \approx 0$.

Remark 2. In the process of deformation the elastic moduli $\bar{E}_1^+, \bar{E}_1^-, \bar{E}_2^+, \bar{E}_2^-, \bar{G}_{12}$ change in the basic experiments as positive monotonically decreasing functions. Therefore the damage variable ω defines a monotonically increasing function.

Remark 3. An accurate measurement of the elastic constants of the orthotropic materials in the initial undamaged field under conditions of uniaxial tension, uniaxial compression and pure torsion is connected with a great experimental difficulties [1,2,6]. That is why it is important to use value $E_1^+, E_1^-, E_2^+, E_2^-, G_{12}$ in the definition of the damage.

DAMAGE INDUCED ANISOTROPY

Let us consider a more complex case when microcracks occur under conditions of complex loading and have its own directionalities 1,2,3. Such a case of the anisotropic damage shall be described by the damage variable as a second-order symmetric tensor $\underline{\omega}$.

For this purpose first recall that the components of the strain tensor at current time are defined by Eqn (11). It is clear that the components of the strain tensor at the moment of the initial damage have the following value:

$$\underline{\mathbf{P}} = \Sigma_e \left(\frac{\underline{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}{\Sigma_2} + \alpha \underline{\mathbf{b}} + \gamma \frac{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}{\Sigma_3^2} \right) \quad (26)$$

Then let us introduce the damage variable as

$$\underline{\omega} = \underline{\mathbf{I}} - \underline{\mathbf{P}} \otimes \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{-1} \quad (27)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{I}}$ denotes the tensor of rank two with components $I_{ij} = 1$ for $i, j = 1, 2, 3$.

Now we consider the particular case of damage induced anisotropy in the conditions of $\sigma_{33} = \sigma_{13} = \sigma_{23} = 0$ and write, for example, linear-tensor constitutive equation (13)

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{11} &= \sigma_e \left(\frac{\bar{a}_{1111}\sigma_{11} + \bar{a}_{1122}\sigma_{22} + 2\bar{a}_{1112}\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_2} + \alpha \bar{b}_{11} \right) \\ \varepsilon_{22} &= \sigma_e \left(\frac{\bar{a}_{1122}\sigma_{11} + \bar{a}_{2222}\sigma_{22} + 2\bar{a}_{2212}\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_2} + \alpha \bar{b}_{22} \right) \\ \varepsilon_{12} &= \sigma_e \left(\frac{\bar{a}_{1112}\sigma_{11} + \bar{a}_{2212}\sigma_{22} + 2\bar{a}_{1212}\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_2} + \alpha \bar{b}_{12} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \bar{b}_{11}\sigma_{11} + \bar{b}_{22}\sigma_{22} + 2\bar{b}_{12}\sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_2^2 &= \bar{a}_{1111}\sigma_{11}^2 + 2\bar{a}_{1122}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + \bar{a}_{2222}\sigma_{22}^2 + 4\bar{a}_{1112}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{12} + 4\bar{a}_{2212}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{12} + 4\bar{a}_{1212}\sigma_{12}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Remark 4. The present model is able to reproduce the damage induced anisotropy. For example, if the stress σ_{12} is equal to zero, we obtain from Eqn (28) that the shear strain $2\varepsilon_{12}$ is not equal

to zero. On the other hand, in the case of zero stresses σ_{11}, σ_{22} we have from Eqn (28) nonzero strains $\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{22}$.

Remark 5. Proposed model is able also to reproduce the difference between the elastic processes in tension and compression as well as the change of the elastic stiffness when the stresses are changing their signs.

Remark 6. We have monotonic strain-stress relations.

Remark 7. Eqn(28) can be rewritten in the following form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ 2\epsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{1111} & D_{1122} & D_{1112} \\ D_{1122} & D_{2222} & D_{2212} \\ D_{1112} & D_{2212} & D_{1212} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

It is seen that the secant stiffness matrix [D] is symmetric. Therefore the Onsager Principle takes place in this case.

Remark 8. The damage loading surface in the plane $\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22}$ has an elliptic form. The loading surface is both continuous and continuous-differential and furthermore convex.

Thus, the proposed model satisfies all requirements which are formulated by Chaboche [7].

Let us apply the definition (27) of the damage variable to the description of the damage in the basic experiments:

- tension in the direction 1

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \omega_{11} &= 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_1^+}{E_1^+} \\ \omega_{22} &= 1 - \frac{v_2^+ \tilde{E}_1^+}{\tilde{v}_2^+ E_1^+} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

- compression in the direction 1

$$\omega_{11} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_1^-}{E_1^-} \quad (32)$$

- tension in the direction 2

$$\omega_{22} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_2^+}{E_2^+} \quad (33)$$

- compression in the direction 2

$$\omega_{22} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{E}_2^-}{E_2^-} \quad (34)$$

- pure direct torsion

$$\omega_{12} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{G}_{12}^+}{G_{12}^+}, \quad \omega_{11} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{R}_{12}^+}{R_{12}^+}, \quad \omega_{22} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{T}_{12}^+}{T_{12}^+} \quad (35)$$

• pure reverse torsion

$$\omega_{12} = 1 - \frac{\tilde{G}_{12}^-}{G_{12}^-} \quad (36)$$

Here $E_1^+, v_2^+, E_2^+, E_1^-, E_2^-, G_{12}^+, R_{12}^+, T_{12}^+, G_{12}^-$ and $\tilde{E}_1^+, \tilde{v}_2^+, \tilde{E}_2^+, \tilde{E}_1^-, \tilde{E}_2^-, \tilde{G}_{12}^+, \tilde{R}_{12}^+, \tilde{T}_{12}^+, \tilde{G}_{12}^-$ are the initial values and the secant values of the elastic constants of the material with damage induced anisotropy.

Remark 9. As well as in the case of an initially anisotropic materials, we obtain from Eqns (31)-(36) that the initial values of the damage variable are equal to zero. Although, actually, it is not true, we may make this assumption, without loss of generality.

Remark 10. The initial values of the elastic constants $E_1^+, v_2^+, E_2^+, E_1^-, E_2^-, G_{12}^+, R_{12}^+, T_{12}^+, G_{12}^-$ must be determined if and only if the considered complex loading creates in the specimens damage induced anisotropy.

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